

Investigation of optimum position of shear wall, bracing system and combination of both in G+30 RCC building by seismic analysis using response spectrum method.

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Abstract

This manuscript presents the analysis of an RCC building with the shear wall, bracing system, and combination for seismic zone III high-rise G+30 RCC building. Nowadays, demand for the construction of high-rise buildings increases day by day due to rapid urbanization and the shortage of land in urban areas. For tall buildings, there is always a need for a proper structural system to transfer lateral loads. There are several structural systems available which usually used for the stabilization of high-rise buildings some of them are as follows: outrigger system, tube system, bundled tube system, core shear wall system, fluid viscous damper system bracing system, etc. Among them, lateral bracing systems are frequently used for structures up to 30 to 40-story buildings to increase their lateral strength and stiffness to fulfill serviceability and design criteria. the bracing system improves the displacement capacity of the building. These types of seismic provisions are used many more times but which one is suitable according to the seismic zone for stabilization of the RCC building will be analyzed in this review. In this work, seismic zone III using ETABs software analysis will be carried out. Study the optimum position of the shear wall, bracing system, and combination of both effects in the RCC building and analyze the result of responses (viz. story drift, story displacement, base shear).

Keywords: RCC building, Shear wall, Bracing system, ETABs, Drift, Displacement.

1 Introduction

Earthquake is one of the natural disasters that challenge most of the engineers in the construction industry [2]. It causes loss of human life and heavy economic losses due to building damages. For the last few decades, structural engineers have been doing research on the characterization and evaluation of structural damage. The different approaches to characterize damage such as ductility, drift ratio, maximum deformation, strain softening, and energy dissipation characteristics at component, element or structural level [5]. The shear walls and bracings both are tremendous techniques that can be implemented in the building to escalate seismic enactment. The shear wall as compared to the bare frame exceedingly improves the overall performance of the structure [1]. The high-rise buildings being built is increasing day by day, reinforced concrete buildings of height greater than 50 m, but less than or equal to 250 m are high-rise buildings, and below that these are low-rise buildings.

1.1 Shear wall system

Fig.1 RCC building with shear wall (<http://www.surl.li/sehxu>)

In the realm of structural engineering, shear walls play a pivotal role in providing lateral stability to buildings, effectively resisting horizontal forces such as wind and seismic loads. As a fundamental structural element, shear walls contribute significantly to the overall performance and safety of structures in the face of dynamic forces. This review paper delves into the extensive body of research surrounding shear walls, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of their design, behavior, and performance. From classical theories to modern advancements, this review synthesizes the key findings and methodologies employed in the analysis and design of shear walls [9]. By exploring a diverse range of studies, the paper aims to contribute insights into the evolving landscape of shear wall engineering, addressing challenges, innovations, and implications for current and future structural design practices. With a focus on both theoretical frameworks and practical applications, this review aims to serve as a valuable resource for researchers, practitioners, and academicians engaged in the field of structural engineering and construction.

1.2 Bracing system

Fig.2 RCC building with bracing system (<https://www.designingbuildings.co.uk/bracing>)

Bracing systems is crucial for enhancing the stability and resilience of buildings under lateral loads, such as those induced by seismic events or wind forces. Among the various bracing systems, structural steel bracing stands out as a widely adopted and effective solution. This review paper delves into the extensive body of research dedicated to structural steel bracing systems, aiming to offer a comprehensive exploration of their design principles, behavior, and practical applications. From classical approaches to contemporary innovations, this review synthesizes key findings from a diverse range of studies, providing a nuanced understanding of the performance and advantages of structural steel bracing. Through an examination of both theoretical frameworks and practical case studies, the paper endeavors to contribute valuable insights to the evolving landscape of structural engineering [4]. By addressing challenges, highlighting advancements, and elucidating implications for current and future design practices, this review aspires to serve as an informative resource for researchers, engineers, and professionals engaged in the dynamic field of structural engineering and construction.

1.2 Response spectrum method

Response spectrum analysis is a widely employed technique in earthquake engineering to predict the maximum structural response of a building to seismic forces. It is particularly useful for evaluating the dynamic behaviour of structures under earthquake loads, allowing engineers to understand how different parts of the building will respond to

ground motion. The method begins with the selection of a set of ground motion records that represent a range of potential earthquake scenarios for the region where the structure is located. These records are typically obtained from historical seismic data or generated synthetically based on probabilistic seismic hazard analysis. Next, the ground motion records are processed to obtain their corresponding response spectra. A response spectrum is a plot of the maximum structural response (such as displacement, velocity, or acceleration) against a range of periods or frequencies. It provides a concise summary of how a structure will respond to seismic excitation across different frequency ranges.

In response spectrum analysis, the structure is idealized as a single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) system for each mode of vibration, where each mode represents a particular pattern of structural deformation. The structural response for each mode is calculated using the modal properties (eigenvalues and eigenvectors) obtained from modal analysis. The response spectrum for each ground motion record is then applied to the SDOF system to determine the maximum response for each mode. The overall response of the structure is obtained by combining the contributions from all modes, considering their modal participation factors and modal shapes. One of the key advantages of response spectrum analysis is its computational efficiency compared to time history analysis, especially for complex structures with many degrees of freedom. It allows engineers to quickly assess the seismic performance of a structure and identify critical modes of vibration without simulating the entire earthquake time history.

2 Overview of literature

Many research studies have been carried out to find out seismic behavior of buildings with shear wall and bracing system separately. Ali Kaveh and Pooya Zakian [1] Reinforced concrete shear wall frame structures the stress ratio of beams is near their allowable boundaries, while for columns, it's lower due to the strong column-weak beam constraint. Optimization aims to satisfy this constraint alongside stress constraints. Achieving an optimal design involves pushing constraints close to their limits while minimizing the objective function. This research focuses on optimal seismic design of RC dual systems, with methods adaptable to RC frame seismic design. A structural model is proposed, and section databases for columns, beams, and shear walls are generated. By adhering to FEMA and ACI guidelines, engineers can reduce costs and automate seismic design optimization, avoiding computational efforts and trial-and-error procedures. Shaik Akhil Ahamad et al [2] The study underscores the importance of uniform stiffness in reducing displacement, with the most favorable results observed in Case C, where shear walls are placed at four ends. Base shear values vary across seismic zones, emphasizing the need for uniform stiffness to distribute lateral loads. Torsional irregularity is noted in Case C, suggesting a requirement for additional stiffness to reduce displacements in all seismic zones in India. Despite discrepancies in time periods, as per IS 1893:2016 (Part-1), the building is deemed safe from resonance effects. Tulay Aksu Ozkula et al. [3] The substantial influence of shear walls on the seismic performance of reinforced concrete buildings is highlighted by this study. Shear barriers affect drift ratios, displacement needs, and first-mode periods, according to ETABS dynamic analysis. The study highlights that stronger and more ductile shear walls lower the amount of damage to structural parts, especially beams and columns. Shear walls with proper design have a significant impact on seismic performance; shear walls with insufficient reinforcement do not improve performance. Shubham S. Shinde [4] The research compares the effectiveness of Shear Wall Systems and Bracing Systems in seismic-resistant structures. For Shear Wall Systems, the model with shear walls along the periphery outperforms others, showcasing a 53% reduction in displacement and a max story drift about one-fourth that of a normal building without lateral load resistance. In contrast, the Bracing System, particularly the X-type bracing, demonstrates a 30% reduction in displacement and a max story drift half that of a normal building. Overall, the study concludes that the Shear Wall System with periphery placement is more efficient than the Bracing System in enhancing seismic performance.

Krupaben J. Patel et al [5] The research highlights the positive impact of steel bracing systems on the displacement capacity, lateral stiffness, and shear strength of reinforced concrete structures. The effectiveness of different bracing configurations varies based on the building shape: Diagonal bracing is more efficient for Square-shaped buildings, X-type for I-shaped, Inverted V-type for T-shaped, and X-type for L-shaped structures. Additionally, the study suggests that introducing bracings can enhance base reaction values in seismic-resistant designs. Overall, the findings emphasize the significance of tailored bracing strategies in improving the seismic performance of diverse building shapes. O. Esmaili et al [6] the research underscores the importance of recognizing time-dependent effects in the design of concrete structures. The presence of differential displacements due to concrete time dependency is highlighted, emphasizing the need for designers to account for varying longitudinal stiffness in structural elements. The study suggests that while seismic bracing systems require a level of ductility for energy absorption, the adverse effects of

axial loads on their performance should be carefully considered. The use of shear walls for both gravity and bracing systems is deemed unacceptable, as it not only places seismic loads on the main walls but also subjects them to a significant percentage of gravity loads. Confinement of concrete in shear walls is recommended for increased ductility and stable behavior. The research emphasizes the influence of axial load levels on the R factor, design base shear, and moment of inertia, providing insights into the trade-offs between axial load and cross-sectional area. Furthermore, the study highlights the impact of concrete time dependency on the premature cracking of coupling beams and calls for simultaneous consideration of time-dependent concrete behavior and construction sequence loading in analyses. The critical demands are found to occur in the middle height of the structure, between the 25th and 35th stories. Shubam Sharma et al [7] research aimed to optimize the seismic response of structures by examining critical parameters such as story displacement, drift ratio, base shear, and overturning moment. The study involved 50 different building models and found that the hybrid structural system effectively minimized maximum story displacement and drift ratio with only a slight increase in base shear and overturning moment. The results demonstrated the efficiency of the hybrid structural system (type-1) across various building heights, especially for medium to tall structures. While the overturning moments were relatively high for 10-story buildings, other parameters such as story displacement, drift ratio, time period, and base shear remained under control. The recommendation is to prioritize the hybrid structural system (type-1) for medium to tall structures, as the reduction in parameters compared to buildings with shear walls is substantial for tall structures and only marginally significant for low-rise structures. The significance of this new lateral load resisting system lies in achieving significant reductions in maximum story displacement and drift ratio while maintaining minimal increases in base shear and overturning moment.

Gopinath et al [8] The research presents a seismic analysis method for a plane reinforced concrete frame with an open soft storey structure, demonstrating its general acceptability and approximate alignment with more accurate methods. The study observes significant lateral displacement in frames with soft storeys, highlighting the efficacy of introducing shear walls in both X and Z directions to minimize corner column displacement. The overstrength in braced reinforced concrete frames is attributed to the added strength from the brace system and the stiffening effects of connections. The number of braced bays is identified as a crucial parameter influencing capacity interaction. Structures without braced frames exhibit weaker seismic performance, with higher ductility values noted for structures with bracing systems. The study utilizes STAAD.Pro software to create models, employing static seismic analysis to calculate displacement and storey drift. Graphical comparisons of displacement vs. storey level and storey drift vs. storey level support the findings, providing valuable insights into the seismic performance of structures with and without bracing systems.

Vineeth Vijayan et al [9] The research concludes that replacing normal RCC shear walls with steel-silica fume concrete composite shear walls in aesthetic tall buildings enhances seismic resistance and provides attractive structural properties. The advantages of the composite shear wall include a significant reduction in storey drift, especially as the number of storeys increases. Compared to normal shear walls, the composite shear wall demonstrates a substantial reduction of nearly 60% in displacement, highlighting its effectiveness in minimizing seismic effects. Additionally, the study underscores the significant role of the composite shear wall in reducing storey shear, emphasizing its positive impact on the overall seismic performance of aesthetic tall building.

3 Modelling

For the study G+30 storeyed RCC hostel building in plan is considered having 2 floors are commercial rest all residential for hostel. The structure is modelled using ETABs software and analyzed using response spectrum method of analysis. Response spectrum method is dynamic method in those only peak values of structural responses of building are taken into account. For enhancing responses of building shear wall, bracings and combinations of both are installed at various positions. Seismic responses compared for 8 different models in G+30 high rise RCC building then optimum position to be find out.

3.1 Modelling of RCC Building and Seismic Analysis

A G+30 storey RCC building is used for study. Table 1 shows details of the building.

Table 1. Details of building

Number of stories	G+30
Total height of structure	93.3 m
Floor to floor height	Commercial=3.3m & Residential=3m
Grade of steel	Fe 500
Grade of concrete	M40
Structural steel (bracing)	ISWB550
Size of column	0.9m x 0.9m for G to 7th floor 0.75m x 0.75m for 8th to 18th floor 0.6m x 0.6m for 19th to 30th floor
Size of beam	0.23m × 0.6 m, M40
Shear wall thickness	0.3m, M40
Slab thickness	0.15m, M40
Wall thickness (non structural)	0.2m AAC

Modelling and analysis of building is done by ETABs software. By modelling beams, columns, shear walls as frame element and slab shell element respectively. The weight per unit volume of concrete is taken as 40 KN/m³. The plan and 3D view of hostel building shown below. 3D model is referred to understand structural behavior of building under lateral loads and default load combinations. Live load intensity 2 kN/m² is considered on all floors and considering seismic zone III with a seismic zone factor (Z) is 0.16 taken from IS 1893-2016 Part 1 Criteria for Earthquake resistant design of structures.

Table 2 Represents seismic parameters of hostel building located in Mumbai taken from IS 1893 Part I Criteria for Earthquake resistant design of structures.

Table 2. Seismic parameters

Seismic Zone	III
Zone factor	0.16
Response Reduction Factor	5
Importance factor	1.2
Soil type	Medium soil
Response Spectrum Method	As per specifications of IS 1893:2016

The importance factor is taken as 1.2 as the building is a residential building. The response reduction factor R is considered as 5 because the building is a special moment resisting framed structure. Soil

type is considered as medium. When a structure is subjected to ground motion, the responses will be influenced by the soil and foundation characteristics. In this study, it is assumed that the building is resting on a stable ground and the structure is a rigid frame, therefore the bottom is considered as fully fixed. Response Spectrum analysis done as per IS 1893:2016 specifications.

From the modal analysis of bare frame, the maximum displacement is 204.84 mm. Here the displacement is under permissible limit $H/250$ i.e. less than 373.2 mm. The storey drift permissible limit is 0.004 times storey height as per clause 7.11.1.1 of IS 1893:2016. For further more enhancement of structural behavior of structure it is required to make structure capable to resist seismic forces and to be strengthened with shear wall, bracing and combination of both.

3.1.1 Bare frame

Conventional RCC building

Model 1 – Bare frame

Figure 3 Typical floor Plan of Model 1

Figure 4 3D View of Model 1

Table 3. Structural Responses of RCC bare frame

Structural response	Maximum value	Permissible limit
Displacement (mm)	204.84	373.2
Drift	0.003515	0.012

3.1.2 Shear wall at corner:

There are two types of shear wall in high rise rcc building.

Model 2 – L shape shear wall at corners

Model 3 – T shape shear wall at corners

Figure 5 3D View of Model 2

Figure 6 3D View of Model 3

3.1.3 X bracing

There is X type of bracing at two positions in high rise rcc building.

Model 4 – X type bracing at corners

Model 5 – X type bracing at edges

Figure 7 3D View of Model 4

Figure 8 3D View of Model 5

3.1.4 Combination of shear wall and bracing

There is combination of shear wall and bracing system at three positions in high rise rcc building

Model 6 – L shape shear wall with X type bracing at corners

Model 7 – T shape shear wall with X bracing at edges

Model 8 – T shape shear wall with X bracing at corner

Figure 9 3D View of Model 6 **Figure 10** 3D View of Model 7 **Figure 11** 3D View of Model 8

4 Results and Discussion

Total 8 models are analyzed by using software ETABS (2018) in which shear wall, bracing and combination of both installed at various positions. Response spectrum method is used for seismic analysis. The maximum values of structural responses namely storey displacement, storey drift and base shear are tabulated below.

4.1 Maximum storey displacement

Models	Maximum storey displacement (mm)
Model 1	204.84
Model 2	136.8075
Model 3	186.8189
Model 4	123.3112
Model 5	98.4001
Model 6	98.2329
Model 7	65.1947
Model 8	78.8417

Figure 12 Maximum storey displacement graph

4.2 Maximum storey drift

Models	Maximum storey drift
Model 1	0.003515
Model 2	0.001841
Model 3	0.002463
Model 4	0.001558
Model 5	0.001277
Model 6	0.001311
Model 7	0.001826
Model 8	0.001036

Figure 13 Maximum storey drift graph

4.3 Maximum base shear

Models	Maximum base shear (kN)
Model 1	5635.6877
Model 2	5629.7316
Model 3	5797.2497
Model 4	5766.2097
Model 5	5717.9701
Model 6	5711.3840
Model 7	5879.6516
Model 8	5884.0593

Figure 14 Maximum base shear graph

4.4 Response of G+ 30 Storeys

Determining the ideal placement of shear walls, bracing system and combination of both within reinforced concrete (RCC) structures is crucial for the overall stability of the building. The strategic positioning of these shear walls plays a pivotal role in minimizing lateral forces that act upon RCC buildings, thereby enhancing their structural integrity. By carefully selecting the locations for shear walls, bracing system and combination of both can effectively mitigate the impact of horizontal forces, ultimately creating a robust lateral force resisting system within the structure.

When designing a building's seismic resistance, the strategic placement of shear walls and bracing systems is crucial to ensure optimal structural stability. By combining these two elements, create a robust lateral force resisting system that effectively minimizes lateral forces acting on the building. Research indicates that the positioning of shear walls plays a significant role in the overall efficiency of the lateral force resisting system. In RCC structures or buildings, a comparative analysis is often conducted to determine the most suitable location for shear walls to be installed. This meticulous study aims to identify the optimum positions where shear walls can work in tandem with bracing systems to enhance the structure's ability to withstand seismic forces.

The shear wall, bracing system and combination of both is installed in the building at different locations and analyzed using Response Spectrum method. The structural responses such as the lateral storey displacement, storey drift and base shear of the RCC building are influenced with shear wall, bracing and combination of both significantly the building's response.

5 Conclusion

From all the G+30 hostel RCC building analysis carried out, within the scope of the work defined, the conclusions are enumerated below:

1. Concerning Codal provisions and permissible limits Structural responses are performing better than Bare Frame when additional provision of Shear wall and bracing at varying positions.
2. As per displacement criteria, displacement of the shear wall, bracing system, and combination of both reduced by 34%, 40%, and 68% respectively than the bare frame.
3. Drift of shear wall, bracing system, and combination of both reduced by 48%, 56%, and 70% respectively than the bare frame.
4. Base shear of the shear wall, bracing system, and combination of both Increases by 3%, 1.5 %, and 4.22% respectively than the bare frame.
5. Optimum position for only shear wall model is Model 2 which is L shape shear wall at corner
6. Optimum position for only X type steel bracing is Model 5 which is X bracing at edges
7. Optimum position for combination of both shear wall and bracing system is Model 7 which is combination of T shape shear wall at edge and X type bracing at central edge.

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